

Deliverable D5.1

Enriched report viral variants and health outcomes

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1. Executive Summary

BY-COVID Work Package (WP) 5 develops multiple use cases to address evolving research questions that arise during a pandemic, requiring data from multiple domains, sources, and countries. This **evolving BY-COVID demonstrator** is continuously enriched with new data, new evidence, and new hypotheses as part of Task 5.1. The use cases implemented in Task 5.2, Task 5.3 and Task 5.4 serve as concrete examples of **adaptable and responsive workflows and methodologies** designed to tackle the changing research challenges of a pandemic.

The **'Baseline Use Case'** developed in Task 5.2 provides a **standard workflow, methodology and supporting technology** that enables it to address any well-defined research question relevant for policy making. The proposed use case aims to demonstrate how mobilisation and linkage of **heterogeneous real-world population data sources** hosted at **multiple sites** can enhance the understanding of the direct and indirect effects of the pandemic on health outcomes in populations crossing jurisdictional borders. The proposed methodological framework provides guidance in the form of a systematic approach to address **federated** cross-national causal research questions in a privacy-preserving way, while tackling challenges at different layers of **interoperability** (legal, organisational, semantic, technical). This flexible workflow can evolve with **new data types** (e.g., socioeconomic and genomic), **new data sources** (e.g., registries, bio-samples, surveillance systems), **new sites** (e.g., other countries), and **new hypotheses** (e.g., COVID-19 Disease Maps).

1.1 Deliverable Scope and Content

The work in Task 5.2 contributes to **"Objective 5.1: Assessment of viral variant and disease outcome using real world data"** by prototyping a federated analysis workflow applicable to any population health research question, including those requiring the integration of viral genomic data. However, the initial scope of Deliverable 5.1, defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) as an *"enriched report on the impact of viral variants on health outcomes"*, has been expanded and generalised to encompass the **full methodological process** of federated (causal) analysis using a variety of real-world observational data sources. We believe that expanding the scope beyond the original agreement will provide a more comprehensive overview of the work carried out in WP5 T5.2.

Although in the original proposal, the Baseline Use Case encompassed the **integration of additional data sources**, such as viral genomic data, the focus shifted due to the actual availability of various data types at a meaningful level of granularity. The emphasis turned into figuring out how to actually integrate those different data sources. Conceptual and practical work delivered several ways forward for integrating data from Social Sciences and Humanities and molecular life sciences.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal .	No
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	Yes
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.	No
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policy makers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	No
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	No
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	No
	3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.	Yes
	4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the on-going European	No

	VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.	
Objective 3 Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19	1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility, and disease pathways.	No
	2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.	No
	3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.	No
Objective 4 Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern	1. Broad uptake of viral Data Hubs across Europe deliver an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.	No
	2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open , normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision making.	No
Objective 5 Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and	1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).	No

European Health Data Space (EHDS)	2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life , SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.	No
	3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.	Yes
	4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.	Yes

3. Introduction

The **evolving BY-COVID demonstrator** is designed for flexibility, enabling it to adapt to new research questions during a pandemic by **integrating data** from diverse domains, sources, and countries. The '**Baseline Use Case**' exemplifies this responsiveness by **prototyping a standardised workflow, methodology, and supporting technology** that can address any well-defined research question relevant to policy making. It is built to **evolve** along the way with new data types, such as genomic or socioeconomic information, new data sources like registries, bio-samples, and surveillance systems, new hubs in other countries, or emerging hypotheses resulting from the COVID-19 Disease Maps¹.

Evaluating public health policies and responding effectively to the evolving situation during a pandemic requires rapid access to diverse **health data**² sources, curated across multiple datasets by various data holders. To assess the impact of treatments, interventions, or exposures in real-world settings involving large and diverse populations, leveraging “real-world” observational data is essential. **Real-world evidence (RWE)** can be obtained through the **secondary use**³ of **real-world data (RWD)**⁴ such as routinely collected health, care and administrative data. Utilising RWD provides valuable opportunities for informing and shaping health policy.

However, RWD often includes **sensitive** personal⁵ health information, which is subject to strict privacy, confidentiality and data protection regulations such as the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Sharing sensitive data outside secure environments is often hindered by privacy concerns, security issues, legal and regulatory constraints, and inadequate governance structures. This imposes further requirements when reusing data for research, such as pseudonymisation and data minimisation, or anonymisation⁶,

¹ A knowledge repository of molecular mechanisms of COVID-19 (see <https://disease-maps.org/>).

² Data are understood as health-related when they provide information on health status or health determinants of given individuals or populations.

³ Secondary use refers to the use of health data from RWD data sources for a purpose that differs from the original intention for which data was collected.

⁴ Real-world data (RWD) are the data relating to patient health status and/or the delivery of health care that is routinely collected by the interaction of a given individual or population with the health system through a variety of perspectives and sources.

⁵ GDPR defines personal data as any information that can identify a natural person, directly or indirectly, such as: names, identification numbers, location data, online identifiers, and one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of a person (GDPR article 4.1). Within this broader category of personal data, the GDPR also recognizes "special categories of data," often referred to as "sensitive data". As outlined in Article 9, these sensitive data types are personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

⁶ Pseudonymisation enables the personal data to become unidentifiable unless more information is available whereas anonymisation allows the processing of personal data to irreversibly prevent re-identification.

depending on the research objectives.

The extensive and continuous **reuse** of sensitive health data could significantly strengthen the impact of population health research on public policy decisions (1,2). Leveraging population health data for **federated policy-oriented research** has been proposed by the “Information for Action” Joint Action (**JA-InfAct**) (3,4) and Population Health Information Research Infrastructure (**PHIRI**) (1,5,6) project, highlighting the principles of **interoperability** at **Legal** (i.e., privacy-by-design), **Organisational** (i.e., analysis coordination), **Semantic** (i.e., built upon a Common Data Model - CDM) and **Technical** (i.e., via the distribution of analyses and a reproducible environment) level.

A sensible approach to bridge the gap between observational studies and public health decision making, preferably based on identifying **causal relationships**, is to emulate a hypothetical randomised experiment, i.e. the ‘target trial’ (7). Applying such a causal framework often implies the need for detailed **individual-level data** in order to mitigate confounding. Therefore, health researchers frequently need to access and analyse personal data, because the research objectives cannot be achieved otherwise. When anonymisation of data is not adequate, de-identification techniques, such as **pseudonymisation**, reduce privacy risks while keeping the data useful for research. To further protect privacy when using pseudonymised data, employing a **Secured Processing Environment (SPE)**, also known as Trusted Research Environment (TRE) or Data Safe Haven, is recommended.

Integrating and analysing real-world observational data from different regions or countries can enhance evidence-based public health decision-making by providing more precise and generalisable estimates. However, conducting causal research **across borders** typically brings challenges in terms of sensitive data access and interoperability (3). Strategies to reduce privacy risks in the reuse of sensitive data from populations crossing jurisdictional borders might be the use of a **federated approach** to data mobilisation where data is kept at holders’ premises, code moves to run the analysis locally, and the output (aggregated data) can be shared and used to perform the overall analyses.

Developing a workflow to emulate a randomised controlled trial (RCT) in a federated manner addresses one of the most **complex** methodological and computational challenges. By tackling this difficult case first, we ensure that the workflow is **robust** enough to handle other potential methodological approaches effectively. This approach not only validates the workflow's capability but also allows for its **adaptation and repurposing** in response to future international health alerts or emerging research needs.

4. Methods

The main objective of the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case is to **prototype a standard workflow, methodology and supporting technology** enabling it to respond to any well-defined research question. The work within Task 5.2 has focused on a **causal research framework** emulating an RCT with observational data in a federated manner. This strategy was selected to tackle the most complex research questions in terms of methodology and computation upfront, ensuring that other potential methodological approaches would also be viable.

The employed causal framework emulates a **target trial**, which involves structuring an observational study or analysis in such a way that it mimics the design and principles of an RCT that could theoretically be conducted, as illustrated by Hernán *et al* (8). **Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs)** were constructed during a workshop, using DAGitty⁷, to encode our subject-matter knowledge and assumptions about the causal structure of interest. For developing the analytical pipeline, only open-source software, such as R and DuckDB⁸, was used.

The proposed methodological framework for federated causal inference (re-)using observational data sources was demonstrated by prototyping a workflow which can be used to assess the *real-world effectiveness of SARS-CoV-2 primary vaccination as compared to partial or no vaccination in preventing SARS-CoV-2 infection in populations spanning different countries.*

The initially defined BY-COVID Baseline Use Case partners were the Belgian Institute of Public Health (Sciensano), Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud (IACS), the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)⁹, the University of Tartu (Estonia)¹⁰, and the Austrian National Public Health Institute (GÖG)¹¹. The Baseline Use Case required close collaboration

⁷ <https://www.dagitty.net/>

⁸ DuckDB: an Embeddable Analytical Database (see DuckDB | Proceedings of the 2019 International Conference on Management of Data: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3299869.3320212>)

⁹ In the **Netherlands**, linking the vaccination register to disease notification data is a lengthy process for data access. Unfortunately, this extended timeline made it impossible to obtain the necessary data within the BY-COVID project's timeframe.

¹⁰ **Estonia** did not participate due to insufficient human resources and difficulties in accessing the required data.

¹¹ In **Austria**, obtaining individual-level data for secondary use and linkages is nearly impossible due to data governance issues. Significant data protection concerns, legal and institutional barriers, and data silos hinder data integration and sharing. While Austria's system of domain-specific person identifiers enhances data security, its proper use is not yet established in data linkage scenarios requiring institutional coordination. Consequently, linking COVID-19 case data with hospitalisation and medication consumption data, though technically possible, faces legal and administrative hurdles. As a result, no comorbidity data were available, which are necessary to mitigate confounding in the proposed research.

between a coordinating research team (also referred to as the '**Coordination Node**') and institutions hosting or being able to acquire access to the required sensitive individual-level data (also referred to as '**Participant Nodes**') to jointly define the research question and data requirements. Eventually, Sciensano, THL, and IACS were able to acquire access to the required individual-level data of the respective sites Brussels and Wallonia (Belgium), Finland, and Aragon (Spain), and were therefore considered as 'Participant Nodes' in the Baseline Use Case demonstrator. The Coordination Node, being the IACS/Sciensano core research team, was responsible for leading the entire process, promoting the collaboration of the participants and producing the documentation supporting the data access application, data linkage, preparation and the deployment of the analytical pipeline.

All the analyses with individual-level sensitive data were performed at the Participant Nodes' premises following their own governance rules and regulatory restrictions. A detailed description of the security measures implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data within the SPEs of each of the Participant Nodes, as well as a description of the anonymisation/pseudonymisation techniques that were implemented, is provided in the published **Data Management Plan (DMP)** (9), using Argos' services¹², specific to each node. Only non-sensitive aggregated results were shared with the Coordination Node.

The further **enrichment** of the Baseline Use Case encompassed the **integration of additional data sources**, for example those data sources originating from Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and molecular life sciences. Two workshops were held to gain insights into the identification, linkage, and analysis of **socioeconomic data** in the context of the Baseline Use Case. The potential integration of **pathogen genomic data** to address public health needs for pandemic preparedness was explored by gathering experiences, perceptions, needs and expectations from multiple stakeholders through in-depth interviews.

With a view to enhance reusability, the digital objects produced in the deployment of the use case and the workflow were published as a FAIR¹³ digital object. In addition, close collaboration with **WP4** was set up, with a focus on Task 4.3 (Analysis transparency, sharing and trusted exchange) and exchanges with Task 4.4 (Open, reproducible workflows for COVID-19 data analysis) with the registration of the workflows involved. A content-wise description of the data quality assurance framework in the Baseline Use Case has been shared with Task 4.2 (Data Quality Control Support). Provenance information was generated for the Baseline Use case and captured in Deliverable 4.3¹⁴. Finally, the Baseline Use Case was showcased through the Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk)¹⁵ (Task 4.1).

In collaboration with **WP2** and **WP3**, the metadata of mobilised data sources within the Baseline Use Case have been made discoverable in the COVID-19 Data Portal through the

¹² <https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/index.html>

¹³ FAIR principles: **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability, and **R**euse of digital assets

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10927253>

¹⁵ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

use of an application programming interface (API) directly harvesting datasets catalogued in the PHIRI Health Information Portal¹⁶. Several workshops and training events, tackling specific topics, were organised in collaboration with **WP6** to increase cross-domain exchanges.

5. Description of work accomplished

5.1 Prototyping a workflow applicable to any policy-relevant research question

5.1.1 Prototyping a research question

The Baseline Use Case, developed in BY-COVID WP5, has **prototyped** a workflow standard that allows responding to PICOT¹⁷ questions. This workflow provides a structured process for the use of real-world observational data **to address policy-relevant questions** to facilitate rapid responses to future pandemics. In BY-COVID WP5 Task 5.2 we have tested the workflow to demonstrate causal inference as a way to address the most complex of the PICOT questions, in methodological and technological terms¹⁸. The methodological framework has been fully described and published by Meurisse *et al* (10). It offers step-by-step guidance (see Figure 1) for researchers assessing public health questions across national borders.

The framework includes the following steps:

1. Define the research question.
2. Establish a causal model using Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs).
3. Translate the causal model into data requirements with a Common Data Model (CDM).
4. Generate synthetic data for script development and testing.
5. Develop an interoperable analytical pipeline using synthetic data.
6. Extract, link, and transform individual-level data to comply with the CDM.
7. Deploy the analytical pipeline in a federated analysis.
8. Conduct a meta-analysis of the local results.

¹⁶ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/>

¹⁷ PICOT or PECOT stands for (P) Patient/Population cohort; (I)(E) Intervention or Exposure of interest; (C): Comparator (if any); (O): Outcome, endpoint, event; and (T) time to (of) exposure or time to event.

¹⁸ Despite the fact that this workflow has been tested for causal inference is suitable to respond to any PICOT research question.

Steps 1 to 5 form the '*conceptual and instrumental phase*' and can be conducted without access to real-world data, while steps 6 and 7 involve working with RWD to achieve step 8 and produce comparable results to inform policy. Step 2 is necessary when demonstrating causal relationships but can be omitted when causation is not the objective. Within the BY-COVID WP5 Baseline Use Case, the workflow was prototyped to assess the *real-world effectiveness of SARS-CoV-2 primary vaccination as compared to partial or no vaccination in preventing SARS-CoV-2 infection in populations spanning different countries*.

Figure 1. The methodological framework consists of several consecutive steps. Steps 1 to 5 are part of a 'conceptual and instrumental phase' within the framework and are conducted by the Coordination Node without access to real-world data. Steps 6 and 7 involve the extraction, transformation and analysis of real-world data within the jurisdiction of each of the Participant Nodes. Step 8 is the final step conducted by the Coordination Node which produces comparable results to inform policy.

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-023-02068-3>.

The Baseline Use Case ensures interoperability across national borders through a federated approach that complies with privacy and data protection regulations. This approach allows the deployment of an analytical pipeline within each data holder's premises, producing aggregated results without sharing sensitive data. By leveraging heterogeneous data sources from different domains and countries, this **federated analysis workflow** addresses policy-relevant questions using a causal framework in a privacy-preserving and interoperable way.

5.1.2 Querying

As mentioned, the formulation of the research question was guided by the **PICO(T)** strategy (11) frequently used in clinical and epidemiological research. The research question directly feeds into a causal model, study design, information requirements and synthetic data (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Overview of the executed steps and produced research objects during the implementation of the proposed methodological approach steps 1 to 4. DAG: Directed Acyclic Graph. EDA: Exploratory Data Analysis. Source: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-023-02068-3>.

A **Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG)** offers a clear graphical method to identify confounding and other potential biases. The DAG constructed to estimate the causal effect of the defined exposure-outcome relationship was iteratively updated based on literature and the researchers' knowledge and assumptions, using the DAGitty web application and corresponding R package 'dagitty'. This approach enhanced transparency and facilitated discussion among the researchers. A Quarto notebook was developed (see file *vaccine_effectiveness_causal_model.qmd* available in the Zenodo publication (12)), generating an interactive report that visualises the DAG together with the identified minimal sufficient adjustment set¹⁹.

The data requirements, identified based on the causal model, are captured in a **Common Data Model (CDM)**, detailing the syntactic and semantic considerations needed for interoperability between Participant Nodes. Each variable in the CDM is characterised by the following elements: (1) the model entity, (2) the variable label, (2) a description of the variable, (3) the encoding system, (4) the variable format and type, (5) the units of measurement, (6) the requirement level, (7) the variable-level validation rules, (8) the variable properties (observed/calculated), and (9) the possible data sources. A customisable template for building a CDM has been created²⁰. The CDM for the current research question is constructed as an Excel file, including tabs for cohort description, model description (characterisation of variables), and detailed descriptions of certain variables (e.g., comorbidities requiring crosswalks) (see file

¹⁹ The minimal sufficient adjustment set is the smallest set of variables requiring adjustment in order to estimate the causal effect of interest under the described assumptions.

²⁰ See Additional File 1 in the following publication:

<https://bmcmedresmethodol.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12874-023-02068-3#Sec36>

vaccine_effectiveness_data_model_specification.xlsx available in the Zenodo publication (12)). International classification systems, such as ICD-10, ICD-9, and SNOMED-CT, were used for encoding variables and specifying crosswalks. The structure of the CDM is presented in Figure 3. A metadata description of the CDM was provided using the Schema.org vocabulary²¹.

Figure 3. The causal model, represented by a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), the Common Data Model (CDM), and synthetic data are interrelated components of the federated causal research framework. Source: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-023-02068-3>.

Synthetic data (see file *vaccines_effectiveness_synthetic_dataset_pop_650k.csv* available in the Zenodo publication (12)), representing the technical and syntactic specifications from the CDM, has been simulated considering several known population-level parameters for the COVID epidemic waves, such as the percentage of the population that had received a primary vaccination schedule during the enrollment period, the percentage of the population that has suffered from a SARS-CoV-2 (re-)infection during the study period, as well as distributions of demographic factors like age, sex, and socioeconomic level. These parameters were based on openly available statistics from Aragon and Belgium (Aragón open data²², Epistat²³, Statbel²⁴) and validated against available individual-level population data from Brussels and Wallonia (Belgium). The synthetic data enabled the development, testing, and validation of scripts without compromising privacy. Furthermore, it proved instrumental in demonstrating the required data for federated analysis. Since synthetic data is generated through algorithms and models to mimic patterns and trends of RWD without

²¹ Schema.org vocabulary was used to ensure standardised, machine-readable information. For more details see <https://schema.org/>.

²² <https://opendata.aragon.es/>

²³ <https://epistat.sciensano.be/covid/>

²⁴ <https://statbel.fgov.be/en>

directly including any real person's data, it inherently lacks a direct connection to any identifiable individual.

5.1.3 Data application and access

For individual Participant Nodes to comply with the CDM specification, linkage of and access to the required (sensitive) data sources for the research in question should be authorised. Each Participant Node is responsible for the data access application process and the subsequent processing (Extract, Transform, and Load or ETL procedures) of the data following the guidelines provided by the CDM specification. However, to facilitate a rapid data access application process, the Coordination Node provided the Participant Nodes with a comprehensive **study protocol** (available as a Zenodo publication (13)) containing the study objectives, planned methodology, and lawful bases for data processing²⁵. In addition, the study protocol facilitates compliance with 'purpose minimisation' principles. Further, the principle of 'data minimisation' is ensured by building and publishing the CDM (12) specifying the data requirements for the proposed research question. A detailed description of the data processing procedures and the security measures within the SPE of each of the Participating Nodes is provided in the published **DMP** (9), maintained using Argos' services. The roles of data controller and processor depend on the specific agreements and legal frameworks within each country or region. In Finland, THL is the data controller for Finnish registry data. In Belgium, Sciensano acts as a processor in the LINK-VACC project, with data providers as controllers. In Aragon, IACS is upstream processor and downstream controller for data linkage activities, with ethics approval obtained by the DSHSPR research group until the end of the BY-COVID project. The reliability of data contributions to the federated analysis is entirely dependent on the data quality assurance processes established within the data governance framework of the participating partner institutions.

5.1.4 Analysis deployment

An **analytical pipeline** was developed and tested with the support of the synthetic data using the R statistical programming language. This pipeline was implemented as sequential Quarto documents (.qmd files) that reflect and report the outputs of different modules (see Figure 4). These modules include (1) Data Quality Assessment (DQA) of the original input data, (2) validation of the original input data to check compliance with the CDM, (3) imputation of missing data, (4) iterative matching of the exposed to unexposed individuals and a covariate balance assessment of the matched population, (5) a descriptive analysis of the matched and unmatched study population, and (6) a survival analysis in the matched study population. DuckDB, a lightweight database system, is used to increase the speed of

²⁵ The data processing is allowed based on general interest (article 6 § 1.e GDPR) and necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, such as protecting against serious cross-border threats to health, or ensuring high standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices (article 9 § 2.i of the GDPR).

running the workflow by enhancing performance when dealing with large amounts of data and complex analytical queries. Detailed documentation of the statistical methods, along with a README file guiding users on script deployment, accompanies the statistical scripts in a dedicated GitHub repository²⁶.

Figure 4. Graphical overview of the developed analytical pipeline, consisting of different subsequent modules, each producing an interactive report. Source: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-023-02068-3>.

The interoperable analytical pipeline was distributed and deployed within the SPE of each Participant Node (IACS, Sciensano and THL). It requires as input the transformed data complying with the CDM specification. **Containers**²⁷ were used in order to improve computational reproducibility by providing a fixed environment dealing with system and software dependencies. A Dockerfile²⁸, containing Docker image construction instructions, was created. This Dockerfile was run to construct a Docker image²⁹, that can be used to build a Docker container. The Docker image can alternatively be converted into a Singularity image, that can be used to build a Singularity container. The image contains application code and dependencies. The application code includes the interoperable analytical pipeline and a lightweight user interface, allowing the participant nodes to execute the notebook without being forced to interact with the more complex notebook interface. Alternatively, for the Participant Nodes not able to install Docker or Singularity container software within their SPE due to local system restrictions (i.e., technical or operational limitations), the pipeline was provided as multiple consecutive scripts implementing the statistical analyses using auditable open-source software.

Several syntactic and semantic **data quality** checks are included in the analytical pipeline by the Coordination Node. These checks ensure that the input data (i.e., the extracted data linked and transformed by each of the Participant Nodes) complies with the CDM specifications regarding information requirements, format, quality, and logic validation rules. The quality assessments produce informative outputs that enable the Participant Nodes to identify and correct inconsistencies or issues in the input data. Additionally, these

²⁶ https://github.com/by-covid/BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case

²⁷ A container is an isolated portable execution environment (including analytical code) presenting a way for transmission of scripts, management of dependencies and consistent execution of the analyses in different premises, decoupled from the local system.

²⁸ Compendium of existing Linux-based technologies able to create isolated execution environments used to guarantee the reproducibility of the executions. See docs.docker.com

²⁹ https://github.com/by-covid/BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case/pkgs/container/vaccine_effectiveness_analytical_pipeline_gui

outputs accompany the final **survival analysis** estimate to aid in interpreting the results and assessing the quality of the inputs and processing.

Executing the analysis pipeline within each site, being Aragon (Spain), Brussels and Wallonia (Belgium), and Finland, produced **local outputs** for each analytical step (as depicted in Figure 4) and a **comparative analysis** in the form of interactive HTML reports (14). The cumulative incidence of documented SARS-CoV-2 infections for contrasted exposure groups obtained from the different sites is presented in Figure 5. The results of the cross-border comparison of the real-world effectiveness of primary vaccination campaigns in preventing SARS-CoV-2 infections have been published (15).

Figure 5. Cumulative incidence curves of documented SARS-CoV-2 infections for both exposure groups, obtained from local analysis in the different sites: Aragon (ESP), Brussels and Wallonia (BEL), and Finland (FIN). Exposed group: primary vaccinated individuals. Unexposed group: un- or partially vaccinated individuals. Source: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4869107.

5.1.5 FAIR publication

By carefully documenting the methodology, using open-source software, and deploying the pipeline within isolated execution environments, we ensured a fully **reproducible** and **transparent** implementation of the analytical pipeline.

Publishing, preserving, and sharing the digital objects (i.e., the individual components of the workflow) according to **FAIR principles** facilitates exchange and promotes reuse within the research community. All the research objects are shared with rich metadata in **Zenodo**³⁰,

³⁰ Zenodo is an open-science initiative indexed in OpenAIR. All deposited content is openly accessible, promoting transparency and reproducibility in research. Digital object identifiers (DOIs) are assigned to all deposited content, making it citable and enabling researchers to receive recognition for their work.

thereby making them *Accessible* and *Findable*. Additionally, the scripts of the analytical pipeline, along with all documentation, are maintained in a **GitHub repository**³¹ given its robust version control system and collaboration features for effective code management. Further, the research objects of the interconnected workflow have been packaged together with their metadata and registered as a Workflow Run **RO-Crate**³², allowing the indication of relationships between entities (16). The RO-Crate and the associated pipeline are also registered in **WorkflowHub**³³. The distributed **Common Provenance Model (CPM)**³⁴ was applied to the Baseline Use Case, aiming at full traceability of the data derivation chain back to its sources. The local outputs and comparative analysis were packaged together in a second Workflow Run RO-Crate³⁵, which references the general workflow RO-Crate as its main process.

Technical *Interoperability* of the analytical pipeline was further promoted by creating a **Docker-based container image** that includes the R dependencies required by the notebooks. In terms of semantic *Interoperability*, the **CDM** specified standards and controlled vocabularies and identified intersections between different classification systems (i.e., specifying crosswalks). Finally, the *Reusability* of the research objects was promoted by providing clear **documentation** (e.g., a detailed documentation³⁶ and a README³⁷ in the GitHub repository) and **capacity-building** activities. In this context, the Baseline Use Case has been featured as a showcase in the **IDTk**³⁸.

5.2 Enriching the workflow with additional types of data

The data requirements for evaluating the *real-world effectiveness of SARS-CoV-2 vaccines* in the Baseline Use Case have been stipulated in the CDM. The necessary health-related data can typically be obtained from Electronic Health Records (EHR), laboratory test data, administrative data, healthcare insurance claims, pharmacy records, and specific registries (e.g. vaccination registry). Integrating additional types of data from other domains, such as **Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)** and **molecular life sciences**, could further increase the number of PICOT questions that can be answered.

³¹ https://github.com/by-covid/BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case

³² RO-Crate is a community effort to establish a lightweight approach to packaging research data with their metadata (<https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>). The RO-Crate of the Baseline Use Case: https://by-covid.github.io/BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case/

³³ <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.502.3>

³⁴ Provenance is information about the history of a documented object.

³⁵ See RO-Crate in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12987289> (ZIP folder containing research objects, RO-Crate Metadata File and HTML preview)

³⁶ https://github.com/by-covid/BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case/blob/main/vaccine_effectiveness_analytical_pipeline/documentation/BY-COVID-WP5-BaselineUseCase-VE-documentation-analytical-pipeline.pdf

³⁷ https://github.com/by-covid/BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case/blob/main/README.md

³⁸ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/prototyping-research-questions>

5.2.1 Socioeconomic data

In population health research, the socioeconomic status (SES) of individuals and their surroundings is often considered a potential confounding factor in many exposure-outcome relationships under investigation. Given that SES has been identified as an important predictor for COVID-19 vaccine uptake (17–19), and recognizing that socially deprived individuals face a disproportionately higher risk of contracting SARS-CoV-2 infections (20–23), SES has been incorporated as a node in the causal model. Consequently, the CDM included SES at **individual-level** as a variable (*socecon_lvl_cd*) in the data requirements. In addition to relationships at the individual level, there is an impact of political and socioeconomic factors on SARS-CoV-2 vaccination trends that are observed in different countries at a population or group level (24). Therefore, the socioeconomic level has also been defined in the CDM at **area-level** as a *recommended* variable (*socecon_lvl_area_nm*) in order to attempt explaining differences in the estimated vaccine effectiveness (VE) between countries/areas.

Two Participant Nodes, Sciensano and THL, had individual-level SES information available for linkage in their SPE. A **sensitivity analysis** was conducted to estimate the impact of (not) accounting for individual-level SES as a matching factor. When comparing the unadjusted (excluding individual-level SES as a matching factor) and adjusted (including individual-level SES as a matching factor) VE estimates in the Belgian population cohort (including residents of Brussels and Wallonia), only a limited percentage change (3.2%) was observed (15). This analysis does not strongly indicate the presence of residual confounding by individual-level SES after already matching for residence area in the Belgian population cohort.

Workshops

To further explore the integration of socioeconomic data in the Baseline Use Case, **two workshops** were held as part of Task 5.1 to foster developments and stimulate community discussion on this topic. Additionally, the data integration process was evaluated, with participants identifying common barriers and potential facilitators related to the identification, linkage, and analysis of individual-level socioeconomic data. A comprehensive **report** has been published (25), detailing individual- and area-level socioeconomic indicators and data sources, their value for population health research, the integration in the Baseline Use Case, and insights gained from the two workshops.

The main findings of the report (25) highlight several key areas for improving socioeconomic data integration. To make socioeconomic data integration **generalisable for future preparedness**, it is essential to address **data governance** challenges, such as issues with data linkage, diverse ownership, and siloed systems. The workshop participants emphasised the need for support structures for researchers in order to navigate these administrative and legal hurdles. Further, establishing standardised data formats could facilitate that socioeconomic data from diverse sources can be integrated for analysis. This

includes adopting **common data models** and **metadata standards** to enable interoperability among federated entities, as well as establishing a **common set of SES indicators** at the European level to streamline data collection, ensure quality, and support data minimisation principles. **Collaborative projects**, such as BY-COVID, involving interdisciplinary teams and cross-cultural perspectives can provide valuable insights, enhancing data integration and analysis for future preparedness.

5.2.2 Genomic data

5.2.2.1 Pathogen genomics

Sequence information from infectious microorganisms is crucial for identifying pathogens, understanding their characteristics, and comparing their genetic relatedness (26,27). Integrating **pathogen genomics** in epidemiological studies enhances public health by assessing disease severity linked to specific pathogen lineages, identifying demographic factors influencing transmission, and detecting mutations affecting disease control measures like vaccine effectiveness. Its value for infectious diseases management was demonstrated during the COVID-19 pandemic by the extensive use of whole-genome sequencing (WGS) (28) and the unprecedented release of SARS-CoV-2 viral genomes in public databases (29). However, challenges include obtaining representative and timely genomic data, disparities in sequencing coverage across regions (30), and variations in data quality, data formats, associated metadata standards, and access procedures (31). The European **COVID-19 Data Platform** supports the management, sharing, analysis, and interpretation of viral sequence data (32), though the deposited sequences may not accurately reflect true trends in lineage distributions due to unequal sequencing capacity across regions and over time.

The CDM of the Baseline Use Case includes the *optional* specification of a variable for the **SARS-CoV-2 variant** at both individual-level and area-level to compare vaccine effectiveness according to different circulating variants. Ideally, variant exposure is confirmed through WGS and linked to patient data via a unique identifier, but this **individual-level** data is often unavailable (33). Alternatively, exposure to a variant can be approximated by categorising infections based on **known variant circulation in specific time periods and areas**, though this method's accuracy depends on a representative genomic surveillance system. Also, viral monitoring in wastewater samples can serve as a tool to monitor the circulation of the virus in the population. However, viral analysis in a pandemic scenario concerning different geographic areas is dependent on the standardisation of sample collection, transport, preanalytical and analytical processing of samples used for viral detection and characterisation³⁹.

³⁹ More information can be found in the BY-COVID Deliverable 5.3b: Hot Spot detection through wastewater surveillance and samples data collection.

Expert consultation

To gather expert opinions on integrating pathogen genomic data for infectious diseases research and prevention in Europe, **semi-structured interviews** were conducted as part of Task 5.2 with seven stakeholders from different countries (i.e., Austria, Portugal, France, Belgium, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Croatia) and fields (including bioinformatics, platform development, epidemiology, health system planning, and surveillance) between January 29th and February 23rd, 2024. Our qualitative approach aimed to explore experts' experiences, unmet needs, and future expectations or prospects regarding genomic data integration for public health and pandemic preparedness. The interviews followed a predesigned interview guide for consistency but allowed flexible responses. Participants received a detailed study explanation and informed consent. With permission, the interviews were audio and video recorded, and transcriptions were generated verbatim using *Descript's* online tool. Transcripts were analysed using thematic analysis to identify **key themes**, each reflecting different facets of the participants' viewpoints: 'Feasibility', 'Data lifecycle governance', and 'Utility'.

Several key elements reflecting the '**Feasibility**' theme were identified. Multiple participants highlighted the need for **robust and sustainable resources** at different levels. Investments to develop, improve, and maintain scalable, secure and user-friendly **digital infrastructures** were presented as being essential, enabling centralised and standardised data collection, storage, and access. The success of these efforts was also mentioned to rely on **laboratory and workforce capacity**, which must be sufficient to support both routine operations and surge demands during health crises. Participants also emphasised that **establishing expertise** in this field is crucial to successfully navigate the complexities of this operation, through providing a foundation for developing robust methodologies. The need for **European-level harmonisation** was noted by different interview participants, such as European-level standards (e.g., data standards, metadata standards, standards for data exchange), regulations (e.g., European Health Data Space or EHDS), recommendations and guidelines. Several participants expressed their viewpoint that the standards should be coming from a higher policy level (i.e., European level), hence top-down decision-making, to reach large scale harmonisation. The requirement for **collaboration** among a diverse array of stakeholders for the purpose of integrating genomic data was pointed out. This includes collaboration between different research teams, laboratories, departments, and agencies, and collaboration of these stakeholders with public health authorities, clinicians, IT departments, and data owners. The **perception** towards the integration of genomic data with health-related data for public health research was mentioned, with participants pointing out that building trust among stakeholders (including researchers, policymakers, the general public) and establishing a positive narrative is important to allow data integration for research. Trust hinges on transparency about processes, purposes and security measures involved, particularly related to privacy and ethical considerations. It was suggested that establishing a positive narrative, where the potential benefits of

integration, such as improved disease surveillance and public health interventions, are communicated could be beneficial.

Different critical aspects were brought up related to the theme '**Data lifecycle governance**', with the data lifecycle consisting of elements such as 'Sampling and Data generation', 'Data collection', 'Data storage', 'Data use or analysis', 'Data sharing', and 'Data reuse'. Interview participants made mention of different '**Sampling**' strategies to select clinical samples for sequencing pathogen genomes (e.g., exhaustive, random or targeted sampling, different coverages), with these strategies indicated to potentially change over time and with the availability of resources (e.g., laboratory capacity, funding). They also highlighted the importance of finding a balance between ensuring a high sampling coverage and the cost of sequencing. It was pointed out that performing sequencing and analysis ('**Data generation**') in a centralised place is of importance. This centralization is seen as a facilitator of efficiency, reducing the complexities that often arise when tasks are distributed across multiple locations. Elements related to '**Data collection**' were also raised. The importance of and ambition towards collecting high quality (e.g., timely, complete, accurate, reliable) genomic data and metadata was highlighted. However, it was exemplified that technical and administrative challenges (e.g., related to retrospective updates or data validation) can complicate data collection, and can potentially cause overhead, amplify workload and bring down the reliability of the data. Concerns related to privacy and data protection in data collection were brought up. Participants acknowledged the importance for data controllers to limit the collection of personal information to the minimum that is directly relevant and necessary to achieve a specific authorised purpose (i.e., according to the data minimization principle). However, participants underscored the need for collecting common and unique sample or person identifiers aiding linkage to other heterogeneous data sources and avoiding data silos. Further, different participants highlighted the requirement for standardised, centralised and pathogen or disease independent '**Data storage**'. The need for substantial data storage capacity to store large volumes of genomic data was also highlighted. Ethical and legal clearance to host genomic data together with (pseudonymized) unique identifiers and/or sensitive metadata should be available. The importance of '**Data sharing**' (e.g., of sequencing and genetic variation data, and resulting statistics) to allow reuse and foster transparency, was underscored by different interview participants. Participants mentioned that genomic data generated within their institution were deposited in genomic repositories like GISAID, ENA, and GenBank, and that non-sensitive data, derived statistics, visualisations and reports were additionally shared on institutional websites. Emphasis was put on the importance of timely data sharing. While slight delays in the sharing of large raw genomic datasets were remarked upon, a clear commitment to quick data sharing was communicated by different interview participants. To continue, aspects related to '**Data reuse**' of RWD sources were brought up. It was stressed that when it comes to linking and accessing sensitive data, obtaining the necessary legal and ethical clearances is imperative to ensure compliance with privacy and data protection regulations. Data access can be obtained by going through thorough

application processes. Further, the importance of establishing a secure infrastructure was highlighted, to facilitate safe data linkage and to provide controlled access to researchers. This infrastructure would serve as a safeguard against potential breaches while allowing for the effective use of valuable data. In cases where individual-level data is not accessible, it was suggested that regional correlation can be employed as an alternative method to derive meaningful insights. It was acknowledged by an interview participant that the discoverability of data for reuse could be improved, by enhancing effective data discovery tools, providing the ability to perform advanced queries on databases to better understand the availability of data. This participant expressed a clear aspiration for a centralised portal, enabling researchers to easily access metadata and identify the appropriate contacts for gaining access to specific datasets across Europe.

Participants underscored the **utility** of the integration of genomic data for public health research, enabling the monitoring of viral variants, their transmission dynamics, and their impact on elements such as clinical severity and vaccine effectiveness.

5.2.2.2 Human genomics

Integrating **human genomic** data in public health research allows the assessment of the impact of genetic factors on health and their interactions with environmental and behavioural factors. This knowledge informs precision public health strategies by identifying high-risk individuals for targeted interventions, potentially improving outcomes (34). Further, understanding host genetic factors related to disease severity can offer insights into pathogenesis, drug targets, and responses to therapy and vaccination. Currently, host genetics is often an **unmeasured determinant** within causal models (35) and its omission could lead to biased conclusions for many policy-relevant research questions. However, the use of human genomic data alongside routinely collected data in health research is challenged by surrounding **privacy issues and technical barriers**⁴⁰ (36).

Host genetics was not considered as a **potential confounder** in the causal model for the vaccine effectiveness research question in the Baseline Use Case, as it did not inform the vaccination strategy during the defined study period. However, with genomic data increasingly accessible in healthcare and the shift towards personalised medicine, host genomics may likely influence future decisions regarding vaccine allocation (37).

COVID-19 Disease Map

Mapping omics data on molecular responses to viral infections onto the **COVID-19 Disease Map** provides context to complex molecular-level data, enhancing its interpretation needed to generate scientific hypotheses⁴¹. For example, differences in host cellular antiviral

⁴⁰ Barriers related to data access and transfer across research domains have been discussed in Deliverable 2.2, available at <https://zenodo.org/records/8101848>

⁴¹ More information can be found in the BY-COVID Deliverable 5.3: Mechanistic analyses via the COVID-19 Disease Map (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10631331](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10631331)).

responses upon infection with SARS-CoV-2 variants can be assessed by leveraging whole cell proteomics datasets to determine host signalling pathways. Additionally, integrating these alterations into disease map models significantly enhances our understanding of cellular processes in a disease context. Therefore, developing an effective workflow for updating proteomics data onto the COVID-19 Disease Map was a valuable advancement⁴². Such computational workflows, including different omics, could be coupled with the causal model to calculate expression profiles for selected subgroups of patients, based on disease susceptibility, vaccine response or other variables. Conclusions drawn from the analysis of molecular mechanisms based on such profiles could be then incorporated back as variables in the causal model for improved estimations.

⁴² Workflow for differential expression analysis in proteomics data and overlaying DEPs on COVID-19 Disease Map: <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/1110?version=1>

6. Results

The work accomplished from *Section 5 “Description of work accomplished”* was disseminated in multiple publications and activities, as presented in Figure 6.

6.1 Outputs

- **BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Study protocol**⁴³

This Zenodo publication corresponds to the study protocol of the Baseline Use Case and provides a work plan, including details on the research team, study rationale, methodology, and ethical aspects.

- **BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Common Data Model Specification**⁴⁴

This Zenodo publication corresponds to the conceptual and instrumental phase of the workflow, and includes the causal model, common data model, and synthetic data for the Baseline Use Case on real-world SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness.

- **BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Data Management Plan**⁴⁵

This Zenodo publication corresponds to the Data Management Plan specific to each of the Participant Nodes (Sciensano, IACS, THL) in the Baseline Use Case, developed using Argos.

- **Federated causal inference based on real-world observational data sources: application to a SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment**⁴⁶

This research paper describes the methodological framework for federated causal inference that has been developed in the Baseline Use Case.

- **Code repository “BY-COVID WP5 T5.2 Baseline Use Case”**⁴⁷

This GitHub repository contains the statistical scripts accompanied by a detailed documentation of the statistical methods, as well as a README file guiding users on the script deployment.

- **RO-Crate “BY-COVID WP5 T5.2 Baseline Use Case”**⁴⁸

This RO-Crate corresponds to the Research Objects (RO) of the Baseline Use Case, more specifically the components of the workflow, accompanied by metadata in JSON-LD format.

- **Workflow “BY-COVID WP5 T5.2 Baseline Use Case”**⁴⁹

⁴³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7825979>

⁴⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13384703>

⁴⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12636106>

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-023-02068-3>

⁴⁷ https://github.com/by-covid/BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case

⁴⁸ https://by-covid.github.io/BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case/

⁴⁹ [10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.502.3](https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.502.3)

This registration in WorkflowHub corresponds to the Research Objects (RO) of the Baseline Use Case, including the RO-Crate above.

- **BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Local outputs and comparative analysis**⁵⁰

This Zenodo publication corresponds to the interactive reports of each main step of the analytical pipeline of the local analyses, an excel file used as input for the comparative analysis, and the results of the comparative analysis. They have been produced using real-world data from public health and the national health system in Aragon (Spain), Brussels and Wallonia (Belgium), and Finland.

- **RO-Crate “Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Local outputs and comparative analysis”**⁵¹

This RO-Crate corresponds to the Research Objects (RO) of the Baseline Use Case, more specifically the local outputs and comparative analysis, accompanied by metadata in JSON-LD format.

- **Real-World Comparative Effectiveness of SARS-CoV-2 Primary Vaccination Campaigns Against SARS-CoV-2 Infections: A Federated Observational Study Emulating a Target Trial in Three Nations**⁵²

A preprint (submitted to PLOS One, 2024) reporting the results of the federated analysis conducted in the Baseline Use Case.

- **BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies using a prototyped workflow standard to federated population health research**⁵³

This Zenodo publication corresponds to the report on the enrichment of the Baseline Use Case with socioeconomic data and contains the insights from two workshops.

6.2 Dissemination and capacity building

- **Workshop “Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs)”**

An internal online workshop was organised on 22 November 2021 to discuss the research questions in the Baseline Use Case and to construct a causal model using a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG).

- **Showcase “Prototyping federated causal research questions reusing sensitive health data”**⁵⁴

This IDTK showcase presents the proposed methodology for federated causal inference based on real-world observational data sources developed in the Baseline Use Case.

⁵⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12987289>

⁵¹ See RO-Crate in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12987289> (ZIP folder containing research objects, RO-Crate Metadata File and HTML preview)

⁵² <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4869107>

⁵³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12771703>

⁵⁴ <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/showcase/prototyping-research-questions>

- **BY-COVID Spring 23 Use Cases Workshop: Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies on vaccine effectiveness**⁵⁵

In April 2023, an initial workshop was held in The Hague to promote developments in the Baseline Use Case and stimulate community discussion. A particular focus was placed on the Netherlands and Belgium, featuring multiple key actors predominantly from the social sciences domain, both internal and external to the BY-COVID project. Preceding the analysis execution, the workshop took an exploratory approach to the topic, concentrating primarily on data infrastructures and the discoverability of data sources within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) field.

- **BY-COVID Spring 24 Baseline Use Case Workshop: Integration of individual-level socioeconomic data for infectious diseases research and prevention in Europe**⁵⁶

A final online workshop took place in June 2024⁵⁷, after the local execution of the analytical pipeline, to evaluate the data integration process and identify barriers and facilitators related to the identification, linkage, and analysis of individual-level socioeconomic data. The workshop targeted researchers (both within and outside the BY-COVID consortium) working with sensitive data and having experience with or being interested in solutions towards the integration of individual-level socioeconomic data for population health research.

- **Webinar on using containers as SPEs in federated research architectures for health data reuse**⁵⁸

A webinar took place in February 2024 and aimed to raise awareness about the importance of using containers for disseminating and deploying statistical analyses, especially for responsibly reusing sensitive health data within a federated research network. It sought to build trust and confidence in container usage for this purpose, explore organisational requirements and potential barriers, and guide participants in troubleshooting and resolving challenges related to deploying containers for statistical analysis.

⁵⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8234104>

⁵⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12168495>

⁵⁷ <https://by-covid.org/news-events/spring-2024-baseline-usecase-workshop/>

⁵⁸ <https://by-covid.org/events/containers-as-secure-processing-environments/>

Figure 6. Overview of the outputs and digital objects.

7. Discussion

All the steps foreseen in the workflow have been successfully implemented and deployed in the Baseline Use Case. The interoperable analytical pipeline was executed by three Participant Nodes, producing the expected outputs. Figure 7 exhibits the elements that have been proven key when implementing a PICO(T) question within a federated solution.

Figure 7. The interoperability layers that need to be addressed for a successful interoperable (public) service - namely Legal, Organisational, Semantic and Technical interoperability. M2M: Machine-to-Machine. (Source: Authors' elaboration)

Nonetheless, applying the proposed methodological framework has entailed several challenges related to data governance and the various layers of interoperability when conducting federated population health research.

7.1 Legal interoperability

The proposed methodology uses the '**data visiting**' principle, or 'code meets data', to overcome data access restrictions. This approach keeps data under its owner's control while allowing federated research without moving the data. However, compliance with the data requirements specified in the CDM necessitated access to and integration of diverse individual-level data sources *within* the premises of each Participant Node⁵⁹. Data

⁵⁹ The protocol's publication in January 2023 set the stage for subsequent data analyses within each of the Participant Nodes. IACS was the first to deliver preliminary results, achieving this milestone within 3 months by April 2023. THL accessed the data in October 2023 and, after debugging, was able to successfully run the analytical pipeline by February 2024, a total of 13 months after the protocol's release. Similarly, Sciensano was granted access to the data in December 2023 and exported their first results by February 2024, also taking 13 months.

application processes under the GDPR imply in most countries the evaluation of a research protocol and DMP by an authorising body, such as a research ethics committee. In the Baseline Use Case, the Coordination Node provided a comprehensive research protocol and DMP tool to streamline this process. Additionally, data access is restricted to the variables as required in the CDM, ensuring compliance with the **data minimisation principle**. However, a **standardised data access procedure** across Europe is currently lacking, and existing procedures are generally demanding and time-consuming. Centralised coordination of data access applications at the European level, as envisioned in EHDS legislation, could accelerate data access and, in time, responses to policy-relevant research questions.

7.2 Organisational interoperability

Extensive **collaboration** with researchers from the different Participant Nodes, but also with experts from diverse research fields was required to build trust across parties and tackle the proposed research question. Indeed, the evaluation of complex public health research questions generally requires the integration of diverse data sources hosted in different sites by different types of data holders, the adoption of complex analytics and technical solutions, and the accurate description of data and research objects from complex workflows (with elaborate interactions between digital objects). The specification of a detailed workflow (the backbone of organisational interoperability) along with the co-creation loops showed to be key for this purpose. **Partnerships** between diverse field authorities can facilitate this type of work; however, these collaborations are scarce outside the context of international and multidisciplinary European projects, usually far from the centres of decision, thus decelerating the responses to urgent public health threats. Setting up a linkage and exchange strategy between the world of science, those holding RWD and decision makers remains essential for pandemic preparedness. Notably, bridging the gap between the research domain and institutions that possess the required data, yet are not necessarily research-oriented, is crucial. The Baseline Use Case has set up the ground to achieve this goal, ensuring a more coordinated and effective response to public health threats.

7.3 Semantic interoperability

Another major challenge in reusing RWD is the lack of standardisation, especially when integrating data from various sources across multiple countries. **Harmonised data preparation**, ideally following international standards, is essential for public health research, particularly in a cross-border European context. The cornerstone of the semantic interoperability layer is the **CDM**, which defines the data entities and their relationships. To harmonise data from Participant Nodes for federated analysis, the Coordination Node specified **crosswalks** that map variable categories (or values) to different classification

systems. However, further harmonisation in data collection across institutional, regional or national borders, and promoting the development and adoption of international standards in different research fields, would greatly improve the consistency, comparability and reliability of studies. Two major options provide solutions for the mobilisation of sensitive RWD - the bespoke CDM as in the case of BY-COVID or the *a priori* standardisation of data collections using a CDM as in the case of OMOP⁶⁰; pros and cons of either solution have been pointed out elsewhere (1).

7.4 Technical interoperability

A consequence of the data visiting principle requires executing the analysis locally. As in federated research, this will happen in different data holders usually from different countries or regions requiring **computational reproducibility**; thus, using a reproducible analytical pipeline as well as a common execution environment. After developing the initial pipeline using synthetic data, the Coordination Node generated alternative input datasets of varying sizes and missing data levels to test its **robustness**. This helped to uncover and address previously unnoticed faults. However, deploying the analytical scripts locally can still lead to unforeseen errors. As a Coordination Node, it is crucial to diagnose and resolve such issues, emphasising the need for monitoring and debugging. In the current workflow the Coordination Node made use of **log files**, detailing characteristics of the run environment, printing messages when a new step of the analytics is reached, and capturing error messages when these occur. However, debugging without having access to the local data remains a challenging task, requiring **extensive communication and collaboration** with the Participant Nodes. For example, between October 2023 and February 2024, there was extensive back-and-forth correspondence between the Coordination Node and THL to acquire the local results. To facilitate effective **collaboration and versioning**, all necessary objects and supporting materials to run the analytical pipeline were deposited in a **GitHub repository**.

Establishing a **reproducible research environment** proved challenging across Participant Nodes due to **local system restrictions**. The Coordination Node utilised Docker containerisation to package analytical scripts along with the required dependencies. However, deploying Docker containers requires specific operating system (OS) compatibility, installation of particular software, and cooperation (trust, resources and willingness) from system administrators of the TREs, which was not feasible for all Participant Nodes. For instance, at Sciensano, the deployment of a Docker container was not operationalised, necessitating the reconstruction of the analytical environment via the manual installation of dependencies instead. At THL, the use of Singularity as opposed to

⁶⁰ The Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) is a common data model for organising healthcare data from various sources.

Docker containers was supported and a Singularity container was built based on the constructed Dockerfile.

As data from population-wide COVID-19 registries were leveraged at each site, a significant **volume of data** was encountered. Additionally, complex analytical procedures (e.g., daily matching) necessary for answering a causal research question were implemented. To optimise runtime and improve performance, the **DuckDB** database system was used. This approach significantly reduced the processing time (run time is recorded in the log file) and systems' requirements for completing the analyses.

Overall, the Baseline Use Case underscores the importance of comprehensive planning, transparency, local capacities to deploy the technology, resilient infrastructure, and continual adaptation to emerging technological advancements for federated analysis.

7.5 FAIR workflow

By **sharing** all generated **research objects** of the prototyped workflow in a transparent and traceable way, we aimed to **maximise the impact** of the current work and **facilitate the reuse** of the described methodology for population health research. The research objects were documented, described and shared to improve their findability, accessibility, and reuse. Through close collaboration with WP4, the workflow was described using **RO-Crate** (packaging the research objects together with their metadata) (38) and submitted to **WorkflowHub** (a platform allowing to describe, share and publish workflows) (39) in accordance with the FAIR principles. Further, a **provenance chain** according to the Common Provenance Model (CPM) was generated (40), trailing back to the origin of different pieces of the workflow. Each provenance component of the chain (e.g., capturing different steps like local data linkage and transformation procedures, the local computation flow, or comparative analysis of aggregated results) was documented. However, using RO-Crate for packaging a workflow for federated analysis (implementing complex analytics, federated deployment in TREs of different Participant Nodes, and adopting containerisation to pursue a reproducible processing environment) with corresponding metadata, presented a novel adoption of RO-Crate. Metadata and provenance info was generated retrospectively and certain information (e.g., details on the deployment of the analytical pipeline within the TREs of the different Participant Nodes) was not captured adequately. Further validation and adaptation of these valuable approaches in broad research contexts presents a way forward in generating reusable federated workflows and maximising public health impact.

8. Conclusions

The BY-COVID Baseline Use Case has developed a **standard workflow, methodology, and supporting technology** to address any well-defined research question. The framework provides a systematic approach to address **federated cross-national policy-relevant**

research questions based on sensitive population, health and care data in a privacy-preserving and interoperable way. The flexible workflow can **adapt** to new data types, data sources, new sites, and new hypotheses. All steps in the workflow have been successfully implemented and deployed in the Baseline Use Case. The **interoperable analytical pipeline** was executed by three Participant Nodes, yielding the expected results and answering the proposed causal research question. Likewise, the Baseline Use Case workflow proved to be effective in building a solid interplay between data holders that hold sensitive RWD and the research community; thus, seamlessly facilitating the mobilisation of sensitive health data. This methodology and its derived research objects are **reusable** and contribute to pandemic preparedness.

9. Next steps

There are two aspects to highlight. First, how **scalable** the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case federated approach may be in terms of being expanded out to more queries and applied across various contexts. Second, to which extent this approach can **enhance pandemic preparedness**, ensuring its effective contribution to managing future health crises.

9.1 Scalability

There are some steps within the data life cycle where the demonstrated workflow may be made more scalable. In particular, a) How to improve the elaboration of the bespoke CDM; b) How to move from a master-worker topology to a peer-to-peer topology; and c) How to reduce the human-to-human interaction in the communication across nodes and increase the programmatic exchange of software and data objects.

Enhancing the workflow with **additional data** can enable responses to an increasing number of policy-relevant questions as they arise. For instance, incorporating outputs from biomolecular studies of disease pathways could refine the proposed causal model, making it a more accurate representation of reality. Furthermore, new data sources can be **seamlessly integrated into the CDM**, expanding the scope and depth of the analysis. This continuous enrichment ensures the workflow remains relevant and robust in addressing evolving research needs.

The current master-worker architecture has heavily relied on the Coordination Node to address any challenges in deploying the use case. However, to address a larger number of research questions and participation from additional nodes, the architecture needs to evolve. Moving towards a **peer-to-peer network** would be more efficient, allowing each Participant Node to dynamically assume roles as coordinator, promoter, or participant. This shift would distribute responsibilities more evenly, enhance collaboration, and increase the network's overall scalability and flexibility. One tool particularly beneficial in a peer-to-peer

network is the **Common Data Model Builder** (CDBM)⁶¹ which facilitates building data models. The CDBM helps users systematically generate a reproducible folder structure for the research project as a Research Object (RO), which can be easily implemented as part of a deployable workflow. Another crucial tool is **ASPIRE** (Analytic Software Pipeline Interface for Reproducible Execution)⁶² which allows users to containerise real-life data analysis pipelines developed in Python or R in a simple, standardised, and transparent manner. This containerisation promotes reproducibility and simplifies deployment in a federated approach.

Transitioning to a peer-to-peer network requires automating as many processes as possible, as the current approach depends heavily on human involvement. Upgrading from a human-to-machine model to a **machine-to-machine** (m2m) protocol exchange is essential. In an m2m scenario, the analytical pipelines running on participant nodes would automatically share local results, enabling seamless joint analyses. This shift will require the integration of additional technical components, such as **authentication, authorisation, and identification (AAI)** protocols, or secure **APIs**. AAI protocols increase trustworthiness in large-scale networks, for example to secure messaging across nodes, provide secure access to the digital objects and automatically update the compilation of local results and carry out meta-analysis.

9.2 Fit-for-pandemic preparedness

The suitability of the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case approach for pandemic preparedness involves several critical elements that fall outside the direct control and capacity of researchers. Key factors span the entire data life cycle, from native data collection through timely data access; data preparation (linkage, standardisation); availability and access to SPEs; and the dissemination of research results to policy makers and regulators.

At the **native data collection stage**, it is essential for real-world health data holders to standardise their data and implement pipelines that allow for continuous data refreshment and systematic data quality management procedures. Ensuring consistent and up-to-date data collection is fundamental to effective pandemic preparedness. **Continuous updates with new data** involves meeting computational needs (e.g., rapid cycle data ingestion) and incorporating visual analytics tools, such as dashboards, to manage and interpret incoming data. Establishing conditions for the acceptance and integration of new results is essential.

During the **data preparation stage**, standardisation plays a crucial role. Utilising an overarching data model and adhering to semantic standards facilitates the integration and linkage of diverse data sources. Prototyping with a CDM and dashboards based on synthetic data is particularly advantageous, as it facilitates the rapid development of new use cases

⁶¹ <https://github.com/cienciadedatosysalud/cdmb>

⁶² <https://github.com/cienciadedatosysalud/aspire>

and the exploration of potential scenarios for future preparedness. This stage should also support rapid-cycle or recursive analyses, enabling quick adaptation to new findings.

In terms of **data access**, it is important to catalogue datasets to make them easily findable. Employing both generic and domain-specific metadata standards supports effective data querying and retrieval, which is crucial for timely research and response.

For **SPEs**, making these environments readily available is essential. This involves providing access to trusted research environments, such as Docker or Singularity containers, which ensures that analytical pipelines can be deployed securely and efficiently.

Finally, when it comes to the **dissemination of research outputs**, implementing procedures for the continuous translation of research findings to health authorities and regulatory bodies is vital. This ensures that research results are effectively communicated and utilised for policy-making and regulatory decisions.

10. Impact

10.1 Measures to maximise the impact

Several key measures have been implemented to maximise the impact of the BY-COVID evolving demonstrator.

Firstly, the proposed approach incorporates **GDPR compliance** through the use of the data visiting principle, which ensures privacy and security by design, and the data minimisation principle by the implementation of the bespoke CDM. This methodology emphasises data protection by keeping data under its original control and reducing data movement, as well as reducing the amount of information required to respond to the research question, thereby meeting GDPR requirements and protecting sensitive information. Additionally, the input data for the analytical pipeline, linked and transformed within each of the Participant Nodes, is a pseudonymised dataset, further supporting GDPR compliance.

A **flexible and adaptable standard methodology** has been developed for deploying **any PICOT research question**. This framework is designed to be continuously enriched, ensuring that the workflow remains relevant and robust as research needs evolve. It allows for the integration of new data and adaptation to emerging questions, maintaining effectiveness and applicability over time.

Transparency and **reproducibility** are central to the approach, achieved through literate programming that thoroughly documents the entire analytical pipeline. This detailed documentation provides clear, well-organised code and facilitates simple environment replication, enhancing reproducibility. This allows other researchers to replicate and validate the work easily, fostering trust and supporting further research.

Furthermore, digital objects are published in **open repositories** to support the dissemination, exploitation, and communication of research outputs and findings. This practice enhances the accessibility of the results and encourages broader engagement with the scientific community.

Together, these measures ensure that our work is impactful, compliant with data protection regulations, adaptable to new research needs, and accessible for pandemic preparedness.

10.2 Seamless integration within the EHDS for secondary use

The WP5 Baseline Use Case has resulted in an exemplary illustration of how to deploy a complex research query with high potential in policy decision-making within the frame of the development of the **EHDS for secondary use**. This achievement is notable across multiple dimensions. At the **organisational level**, Participant Nodes in the BY-COVID Baseline Use Case are actual data holders or potential health data access bodies (HDAB) within the EHDS, seamlessly integrating the workflow into the data governance and infrastructure framework. At the **semantic level**, the fit-for-purpose approach of the CDM ensures compatibility with future advancements in semantic interoperability. At the **technical level**, the infrastructure has been designed with reusability in mind, positioning it to support the deployment of TREs within the EHDS secure process environments and its federated approach.

11. References

1. González-García J, González-Galindo J, Estupiñán-Romero F, Thißen M, Lyons RA, Telleria-Orriols C, et al. PHIRI: lessons for an extensive reuse of sensitive data in federated health research. *Eur J Public Health*. 2024 Jul 1;34(Supplement_1):i43–9.
2. Agyapon-Ntra K, McSharry PE. A global analysis of the effectiveness of policy responses to COVID-19. *Sci Rep*. 2023 Apr 6;13(1):5629.
3. González-García J, Estupiñán-Romero F, Tellería-Orriols C, González-Galindo J, Palmieri L, Fagaralli A, et al. Coping with interoperability in the development of a federated research infrastructure: achievements, challenges and recommendations from the JA-InfAct. *Archives of Public Health*. 2021 Dec 9;79(1):221.
4. Abboud LA, Bogaert P, Fehr A, Urbanski D, Tolonen H, Noguer-Zambran I, et al. The new Joint Action on Health Information: information for action (InfAct)! *European Journal of Public Health*. 2018 Nov 1;28(suppl_4):cky213.651.
5. Bogaert P, Schutte N. Towards a Population Health Information Research Infrastructure. *European Journal of Public Health*. 2021 Oct 1;31(Supplement_3):ckab164.572.
6. Gonzalez-Garcia J. What the PHIRI federated research infrastructure has achieved so far? *European Journal of Public Health*. 2022 Oct 1;32(Supplement_3):ckac129.467.
7. Hernán MA, Robins JM. Using Big Data to Emulate a Target Trial When a Randomized Trial Is Not Available. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2016 Apr 15;183(8):758–64.
8. Hernán MA, Wang W, Leaf DE. Target Trial Emulation: A Framework for Causal Inference From Observational Data. *JAMA*. 2022 Dec 27;328(24):2446–7.
9. Bernal-Delgado E, Van Goethem N. BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Data Management Plan. 2024 Jun 30 [cited 2024 Jul 4]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/12636106>
10. Meurisse M, Estupiñán-Romero F, González-Galindo J, Martínez-Lizaga N, Royo-Sierra S, Saldner S, et al. Federated causal inference based on real-world observational data sources: application to a SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2023 Oct 23;23(1):248.
11. Riva JJ, Malik KMP, Burnie SJ, Endicott AR, Busse JW. What is your research question? An introduction to the PICOT format for clinicians. *J Can Chiropr Assoc*. 2012 Sep;56(3):167–71.
12. BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Common Data Model Specification. [cited 2024 Aug 29]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/13384703>
13. Meurisse M, Van Goethem N, Estupiñán-Romero F, González-Galindo J, Royo-Sierra S, Martínez-Lizaga N, et al. BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Study protocol. 2023 Jan 23 [cited 2023 Feb 9]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/record/7551181>
14. Meurisse M, Estupiñán-Romero F, Van Goethem N, Perola M, Paajanen T, Bernal-Delgado E. BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: SARS-CoV-2 vaccine effectiveness assessment - Local outputs and comparative analysis. 2024 May 17 [cited 2024 Jun 25]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/11209363>
15. Meurisse M, Estupiñán-Romero F, Perola M, Paajanen T, Gonzalez-Galindo J, Van Goethem N, et al. Real-world comparative effectiveness of SARS-CoV-2 primary vaccination campaigns against SARS-CoV-2 infections: a federated observational study emulating a target trial in three nations [Internet]. SSRN Preprint; 2024. Available from: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4869107

16. Leo S, Crusoe MR, Rodríguez-Navas L, Sirvent R, Kanitz A, De Geest P, et al. Recording provenance of workflow runs with RO-Crate [Internet]. arXiv; 2024 [cited 2024 Jul 30]. Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2312.07852>
17. Lillebråten A, Todd M, Dimka J, Bakkeli NZ, Mamelund SE. Socioeconomic status and disparities in COVID-19 vaccine uptake in Eastern Oslo, Norway. *Public Health Pract (Oxf)*. 2023 May 28;5:100391.
18. Saban M, Myers V, Ben-Shetrit S, Wilf-Miron R. Socioeconomic gradient in COVID-19 vaccination: evidence from Israel. *International Journal for Equity in Health*. 2021 Nov 8;20(1):242.
19. Cavillot L, Van Loenhout J, Catteau L, Van den Borre L, De Pauw R, Blot K, et al. COVID-19 vaccination uptake in Belgium: socioeconomic and sociodemographic disparities. *European Journal of Public Health*. 2022 Oct 1;32(Supplement_3):ckac129.046.
20. Vandentorren S, Smaïli S, Chatignoux E, Maurel M, Alleaume C, Neufcourt L, et al. The effect of social deprivation on the dynamic of SARS-CoV-2 infection in France: a population-based analysis. *The Lancet Public Health*. 2022 Mar 1;7(3):e240–9.
21. Godefroy R, Lewis J. What explains the socioeconomic status-health gradient? Evidence from workplace COVID-19 infections. *SSM - Population Health*. 2022 Jun 1;18:101124.
22. Patel JA, Nielsen FBH, Badiani AA, Assi S, Unadkat VA, Patel B, et al. Poverty, inequality and COVID-19: the forgotten vulnerable. *Public Health*. 2020 Jun;183:110–1.
23. Geranios K, Kagabo R, Kim J. Impact of COVID-19 and Socioeconomic Status on Delayed Care and Unemployment. *Health Equity*. 2022 Feb 2;6(1):91–7.
24. Chauhan R, Varma G, Yafi E, Zuhairi MF. The impact of geo-political socio-economic factors on vaccine dissemination trends: a case-study on COVID-19 vaccination strategies. *BMC Public Health*. 2023 Nov 2;23(1):2142.
25. Van Goethem N, Meurisse M, Estupiñán Romero F, Bernal-Delgado E, Kalaitzi V, Saldner S. BY-COVID - WP5 - Baseline Use Case: Integration of socioeconomic data in observational studies using a prototyped workflow standard to federated population health research [Internet]. Zenodo; 2024. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12771703>
26. Kan B, Zhou H, Du P, Zhang W, Lu X, Qin T, et al. Transforming bacterial disease surveillance and investigation using whole-genome sequence to probe the trace. *Front Med*. 2018 Feb 1;12(1):23–33.
27. Van Goethem N, Struelens MJ, De Keersmaecker SCJ, Roosens NHC, Robert A, Quoilin S, et al. Perceived utility and feasibility of pathogen genomics for public health practice: a survey among public health professionals working in the field of infectious diseases, Belgium, 2019. *BMC Public Health*. 2020 Aug 31;20(1):1318.
28. Alm E, Broberg EK, Connor T, Hodcroft EB, Komissarov AB, Maurer-Stroh S, et al. Geographical and temporal distribution of SARS-CoV-2 clades in the WHO European Region, January to June 2020. *Eurosurveillance*. 2020 Aug 13;25(32):2001410.
29. Tosta S, Moreno K, Schuab G, Fonseca V, Segovia FMC, Kashima S, et al. Global SARS-CoV-2 genomic surveillance: What we have learned (so far). *Infect Genet Evol*. 2023 Mar;108:105405.
30. Ohlsen EC, Hawksworth AW, Wong K, Guagliardo SAJ, Fuller JA, Sloan ML, et al. Determining Gaps in Publicly Shared SARS-CoV-2 Genomic Surveillance Data by Analysis of Global Submissions. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2022 Dec;28(Suppl 1):S85–92.
31. The UK Government Department of Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy.

- Intelligent open science: a case study of viral genomic data sharing during the COVID-19 pandemic. 2022 Nov; Available from: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1118628/intelligent-open-science.pdf
32. Rahman N, O’Cathail C, Zyoud A, Sokolov A, Munnink BO, Grüning B, et al. Mobilisation and analyses of publicly available SARS-CoV-2 data for pandemic responses [Internet]. *Bioinformatics*; 2023 Apr [cited 2023 Sep 14]. Available from: <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/2023.04.19.537514>
 33. Meurisse M, Van Oyen H, Blot K, Catteau L, Serrien B, Klamer S, et al. Evaluating methodological approaches to assess the severity of infection with SARS-CoV-2 variants: scoping review and applications on Belgian COVID-19 data. *BMC Infectious Diseases*. 2022 Nov 11;22(1):839.
 34. Kwok AJ, Mentzer A, Knight JC. Host genetics and infectious disease: new tools, insights and translational opportunities. *Nat Rev Genet*. 2021 Mar;22(3):137–53.
 35. Van Goethem N, Serrien B, Vandromme M, Wyndham-Thomas C, Catteau L, Brondeel R, et al. Conceptual causal framework to assess the effect of SARS-CoV-2 variants on COVID-19 disease severity among hospitalized patients. *Archives of Public Health*. 2021 Oct 25;79(1):185.
 36. Daniels H, Jones KH, Heys S, Ford DV. Exploring the Use of Genomic and Routinely Collected Data: Narrative Literature Review and Interview Study. *J Med Internet Res*. 2021 Sep 24;23(9):e15739.
 37. Bruce J, Johnson SB. Exploring the ethics of genetic prioritisation for COVID-19 vaccines. *Eur J Hum Genet*. 2022 Aug;30(8):875–9.
 38. Meurisse M, Estupiñan-Romero F, Van Goethem N, González-Galindo J, Royo-Sierra S, Bernal-Delgado E. BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case [Internet]. GitHub; [cited 2024 Jun 3]. Available from: https://by-covid.github.io/BY-COVID_WP5_T5.2_baseline-use-case/
 39. Bernal-Delgado E, Van Goethem N, Estupiñan-Romero F, Meurisse M, González-Galindo J, Martínez-Lizaga N, et al. BY-COVID WP5 T5.2 Baseline Use Case. *WorkflowHub*. [Internet]. 2024. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.48546/WORKFLOWHUB.WORKFLOW.502.3>
 40. Wittner R, Soiland-Reyes S, Leo S, Meurisse M, Hermjakob H. BY-COVID D4.3 Provenance model for infectious diseases [Internet]. Zenodo; 2024 Apr [cited 2024 Jul 2]. Available from: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10927252>